

SUSTAINABLE LIVELYHOODS AND EDUCATION: EXPLORING THE RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN ENVIRONMENTAL FACTORS AND SCHOOL ATTENDANCE AMONG SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS IN KONTAGORA NIGER STATE

BY

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ABSTRACT

This study explores the role of environment on school attendance for promoting sustainable livelihoods among secondary school students in kontagora, Niger state. The study investigated the environmental factors such as infrastructure, resources and physical environment that affect learning outcomes, specifically in kontagora. The research was conducted using survey research design through a case study approach, utilizing both quantitative and qualitative methods of data collection. The population of the study comprised of all secondary school students in kontagora. Using simple random sampling, a sample size of 80 students were randomly selected for the study. A researcher self designed questionnaire tagged 'Relationship between Environmental Factors and School Attendance among Secondary School Students Questionnaire' (REFSASS) was used as instrument for data collection. Mean and simple percentage was used to answer the research questions while the hypothesis was tested using Spearman rank correlation analysis. Findings from the study revealed that there are several key environmental factors that significantly impact school attendance, which include distance, means of transportation, insecurity, and attractiveness of the school environment, amongst others. These findings have highlighted the challenges faced by schools and the significant implication on students skills acquisition drive for sustainable development, practices and livelihoods in communities. The study's results have implication for policy and practice particularly in terms of resource allocation, infrastructure development, community engagement and teacher support in schools for a more sustainable and resilient community.

Keywords: *physical environment, environmental influence, community, parental support, school design*

INTRODUCTION

The secondary school stage is a crucial stage in any system of education all over the globe. In Nigeria, it is the stage that immediately follows the primary education stage where an individual begins the process of decision making on career and general outlook on life as indicated in the broad goals of secondary education outlined in the National Policy on Education (2014). The performances of students at this stage determine their developmental abilities to themselves and the coming generations. It is a fact that the global challenge of the future prospect of any nation is fundamental to the educational performances of its work force. (Udo & Chuks, 2010, Silvia & Franktisek, 2021). Decline in the performances of students in Africa and Nigeria in particular is evident from cross sectional studies and results of National examination bodies (WAEC, NECO, JAMB) in recent years. In line with the millennium development goals, it is strongly believed that the quality of education is as important as school enrolment (Tinni, 2020, Silvia & Franktisek, 2021). Achieving free education in Niger State means more than just enrolment. It also encompasses staying in school to acquire quality education. A lot of studies have been carried out to determine the interfaces between school attendance, academic achievement and equal educational opportunities. It was observed that there is a direct correlation between school attendance and academic achievement. (Nartley, 2023). Like

other parts of Nigeria, many schools in Niger State have very poor facilities and are not well designed or managed to provide all round experiences. Most of the schools appear as if nothing serious or amazing is happening inside them. The school should be places where knowledge is celebrated, where young minds get inspired and where their future matter. (Pacalat, 2011, Ismail, 2019).

School plant (teachers, curriculum, facilities have a great influence on students' reasons for staying in school because it is from that basis that students form opinion of themselves and how the society perceives them which eventually influences the quality of their input and output in the global society. Any school that is predictably bland and uninspiring in terms of its layout or design, and a home or family that is devoid of care, concern and support for its members, gives students the message about the level of concern and care they are worth concerning their place in the society which shapes their behavior into appropriate or inappropriate. (Peter, 2012, Adedapo, 2019). Most school buildings across the country were built over a decade ago hence, most of them have lost their gusto in the sense that students do not have fun going to them and have the opportunity to learn in them, and the teachers are not excited to have the privilege to teach in them, as there is nothing in the school environment that the teachers can use to inspire the students into believing that the future is indeed bright and promising. (Pacalat, 2011 Adedapo, 2019)

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Environment as defined by Oladunde- Aiyedun, (2022), refers to a sum total of all the living and non living elements and their effects that influences animals, human life and resources in a system. That it is one's surroundings, home, school, garden, shop, hills, and rivers. Also that environment is where one lives or where one carries out one activity or the other. According to Mark,(2014), environmentalists like Albert Bandura and Julian B. Rotter, in their social learning theories, portrays that environment is what shape learning and behavior. This means that behavior and learning are reactions to the environment. This perspective encourages families, school, and educators to understand that the individual develop and learn new skill in reaction to items he or she find around him or her. They find the environment as an important factor in learning and development of the young mind. The social learning concepts focus on the idea that personality represents an interaction of an individual with the environment. This means that the combination of the environment, individual and his reaction encourages behavior and learning. That when the environment is altered, greater learning and educational opportunities increase. Whether in the home or school, creating an environment conducive and supportive of learning aids the minds of students towards evolution to greater knowledge. (Pakalat, 2011, Ihekoronye, 2020). This theory offers the ability to influence the learners' interest positively towards school attendance by changing the environment hence its relevance to this study.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

One of the goals of education according to the National Policy on Education (2014) is to prepare an individual for useful leaving within the society. In Niger state, education is made the major industry for the actualization of the states' vision of becoming one of the best three economies by the year 20/ 30. The state Ministry of Education is tasked with repositioning education at all levels especially the secondary school level. Unfortunately, despite the free education declared by the state government a lot of students do not attend school and where they attend, they do not stay till closing time. What could be responsible for this? Could it be that settlement of school fees is not the only issue that hinders school attendance? This study

therefore is to investigate the factors within the environment that have influence on students' school attendance at the secondary school level in Kontagora, Niger state.

PURPOSE OF THE STUDY

The general purpose is to determine the factors in the environment that influence school attendance of secondary school students in Kontagora, Niger state. Specifically, the study

1. Identified parental factors that influence school attendance among secondary school students in Kontagora
2. Examined the extent to which school design/layout influence students' school attendance among secondary school students in Kontagora

Research

1. What is the relationship between parental support/encouragement and students' school attendance?
2. What is the relationship between school layout/design and students' school attendance?
3. Are there significant differences in parental support and school design quality between public and private school students?

HYPOTHESIS Ho 1: There is no significant statistical relationship between parental support/encouragement with students' school attendance.

Ho 2: There is no significant statistical relationship between school layout/design with students' school attendance.

AREA OF STUDY

The area of study is Kontagora which is a major town on the south bank of Kontagora River in the North West of Niger state. It is the capital city of the Kontagora emirate.

SCOPE OF THE STUDY

This study covered two areas among the numerous environmental factors that influence school attendance. The areas selected are: Parental support/encouragement and School design/layout.

RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design for this study is survey. Survey research design is a quantitative research method where data is collected from a sample or the entire population through questionnaires or interviews to describe characteristics, opinions, behaviors, or attitudes. In this study, attempt was made to identify how environmental factors such as parental support/encouragement and school design influence school attendance among secondary school students in Kontagora.

POPULATION

The target population for this study comprised of all private and public secondary schools students in kontagora town.

SAMPLE AND SAMPLING PROCEDURE

Random sampling technique was used to select eight schools. Four private schools, and four public schools. 80 students were randomly selected as respondents to the “Relationship between Environmental Factors and School Attendance among Secondary School Students ”questionnaire (REFSASS). The respondents sampled were 40 students from both private and public secondary school students in kontagora.

INSTRUMENT FOR DATA COLLECTION

The instrument for data collection for this study is questionnaire tagged “Relationship between Environmental Factors and School Attendance among Secondary School Students” (REFSASS), develop by the researcher for data collection in this study. In designing the instrument, items were drawn from areas that are deemed by the researcher to be of influence to students’ school attendance. The items center on: parental support/encouragement, and school layout/design. The instrument contains 10 items, five each on parental support/encouragement and indicators of school design/layout. Respondents were expected to respond with a simple yes /no options. The instrument was tested and cronbach alpha reliability coefficient was calculated and a value of 0.87 was obtained which indicated high reliability for the instrument.

DATA PRESENTATION, ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION TABLE 1:

Table 1 displayed weighted percentage of Students’ responses to parental support/encouragement and school design/layout.

Table 1: Weighted percentage Response

	Items	Public schools		Private schools	
		yes	no	Yes	no
		98%	2%	100%	0
1	My parents support me with books.				
2	My parents always check my home work/class work.	58%	42%	98%	2%
3	My parents support me with transportation to my school	58%	42%	97%	3%
4	My parents ensure my school uniform is complete.	56%	44%	99%	1%
5	My parents are actively engaged in my school activities.	55%	55%	100	0
6	My school has a welcoming atmosphere.	15%	85%	5%	95%

7	I easily get bored in school.	90%	10%	2.50%	97.50%
8	My school is attractive to me	4%	96%	99%	1%
9	I feel safe in my school environment	5%	95%	100%	0%
10	Everything is available in my school	5%	95%	100%	0%

RESEARCH QUESTIONS (RQ)

RQ1: What is the level of parental support/encouragement received by students in public versus private secondary schools in Kontagora?

RQ2: To what extent does parental support/encouragement influence school attendance patterns among secondary school students?

RQ3: Are there significant differences in parental support and school design quality between public and private school students?

ANSWER TO RESEARCH QUESTIONS

To answer the research questions, descriptive statistics (Mean (M), Standard Deviation (SD), percentages) were used. Normality of data distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Since the data did not meet normality assumptions (all $p < 0.001$). Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics calculated to analyze the research questions.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Environmental Factor	Public Schools (n=40)	Private Schools (n=40)	Mean Difference	Significance (p)
Parental Support	M = 3.23, SD = 2.02	M = 4.95, SD = 0.32	1.72	<0.001
School Design	M = 0.40, SD = 0.93	M = 4.93, SD = 0.35	4.53	<0.001
Overall Attendance	M = 1.99, SD = 1.48	M = 4.93, SD = 0.66	2.94	<0.001

Answer to RQ1: Private schools demonstrate significantly higher levels of parental support (M = 4.95, SD = 0.32) compared to public schools (M = 3.23, SD = 2.02). The most notable disparities were observed in areas such as homework monitoring (40% gap), transportation support (40%), and provision of uniforms (45%).

Answer to RQ2: A strong positive correlation was observed between parental support and school attendance ($\rho = 0.738, p < 0.001$), indicating that parental support accounts for approximately 54.5% of the variance in students' attendance patterns.

ANSWER TO RQ3: There are highly significant differences in both parental support (mean difference = 1.72, $p < 0.001$) and school design quality (mean difference = 4.53, $p < 0.001$) between the groups.

TEST OF HYPOTHESIS

Non-parametric Spearman rank correlation was used to test the hypotheses about relationships between environmental factors and school attendance. Mann-Whitney U tests were conducted to compare differences between public and private schools. A null hypothesis (H_0) posits that if the Spearman correlation coefficient (ρ) equals zero, it implies that there is no correlation between the variables. In contrast, the alternative hypothesis (H_1) proposes that ρ is not equal to zero, indicating the presence of a significant correlation between the variables.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant relationship between parental Support/encouragements on private and public school students' school attendance.

From Table 3, the Spearman rank correlation analysis revealed a strong positive correlation between parental support and school attendance ($\rho = 0.738, p < 0.001, 95\% \text{ CI: } 0.588 \text{ to } 0.888$). This coefficient represents a large effect size, with parental support accounting for approximately 54.5% of the variance in students' attendance scores. Accordingly, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between parental support/encouragement and students' school attendance.

Table 3: Analysis of public and private school students on the effect of parental support/encouragement on students' school attendance.

Statistic	Value
Correlation Coefficient (ρ)	0.7381
P-value	< 0.001
Effect Size	Large
Variance Explained (%)	54.50%
95% Confidence Interval (CI)	[0.588, 0.888]
Decision	Reject H_0 – Significant positive correlation exists

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant relationship between school layout/design on private and public school students' school attendance.

Spearman rank correlation analysis revealed a very strong positive correlation between school design and school attendance ($\rho = 0.840$, $p < 0.001$, 95% CI: 0.720 to 0.961) as shown in Table 4. This correlation indicates a large effect size, with the quality of school design accounting for approximately 70.6% of the variance in student attendance scores. Based on this result, we reject the null hypothesis and conclude that there is a statistically significant and positive relationship between school layout/design and students' school attendance.

Table 4: Analysis of public and private school students on the effect of school layout/design on students' school attendance.

Statistic	Value
Correlation Coefficient (ρ)	0.8403
P-value	< 0.001
Effect Size	Large
Variance Explained (%)	70.60%
95% Confidence Interval (CI)	[0.720, 0.961]
Decision	Reject H_0 – Significant positive correlation exists

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Parental support/encouragement:

Before children can receive instruction and develop skills, they have to get to school every day. Parents have the vital role in supporting their children's consistent attendance in school as this ensures children's success in school and beyond. From the view of respondents, who are secondary school students, almost all of them receive support and encouragement from their parents either in terms of payment of school fees, books, or transportation. Lack of any of these was mentioned as barriers to school attendance in the Leave No Child Behind (NCLB) Act of 2015 adopted by the United Nations, New York. (Joshua & Grooms, 2018). Some of them also have their parents showing interest in their schooling by checking their uniforms, homework or class work. When parents carry out these duties, students have no excuse not to go to school because it is often due to one deficiency or the other that students stay away from school.

School layout/design:

There is no doubt that a serene environment is conducive not only for learning, but for quality thinking and decision making. (Pacalat, 2011). From the responses of students, it was revealed that school layout/design positively affects students' school attendance. This agrees with the findings of Uche, (2023), which established that achievement and students' attendance significantly increased when school aesthetics are in

place. Apart from adequate classrooms and furniture, an attractive school environment can appeal to students' sense of recreation which they always seek to satisfy elsewhere if not available in the school.

SUMMARY OF FINDINGS

From the analysis, it can be deduced that all the responses from students and results of the two hypotheses are favorable and positive. The major findings therefore are:

- i. Parental support/encouragement has a positive effect on students' school attendance and eventual stay in school.
- ii. School layout/design can attract or distract student from attending or staying in school.

IMPLICATION OF THE STUDY

The findings of this study have implication on government, school administrators/proprietors, parents and students. The vision 20/30 of Niger state government is- according to the state government – only realizable through education (M.O E.,2021). If this is the case, then schools need to be made relevant to this aspiration. How relevant schools are, depends on how attractive and interesting they are for students to want to go into them to stay and learn. Here then comes the role of school administrators/proprietors of ensuring attractive and appealing school environment to keep students in school for quality skill acquisition to become useful members of the larger society for National development.

The implication on the parent has to do with attitudinal change on the part of students as far as school attendance is concerned. When parents show support encouragement or interest, students' attitude to school attendance, positively change.

RECOMMENDATIONS

This study is of the view that no individual wants to become irrelevant in the society due to lack education. Hence, the study recommends that:

- i. Parents should reciprocate the government gesture of free education by being more interested and active in their wards' education, and should also not relent in giving their support/encouragement no matter how little as this tells a lot on students' attitude to school attendance.
- ii. Government and school owners should make it a point of duty to ensure that school environment is exceptionally beautified and made attractive alongside the availability of vital school resources.
- iii. Schools especially public schools should design programmes to encourage parental participation like open days and should also outline the school expectation of parents and communicate regularly to parents concerning what the children are learning.

CONCLUSION

Beautiful surroundings and availability of facilities appeal to students' sense of attraction to school attendance. In as much as students have a liking for their learning environment, it is not possible that they will be bored or have the feeling of going away from it. Students' presence in school is no doubt concomitant to Niger state government's vision 2030 aims to ensure that all citizens have equitable access to quality education regardless of their background utilizing the education industry as the major tool to make the vision feasible.

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